

Exploring Different Ways to Store Toothbrush: A Systematic Update of Literature

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Abstract:

Background: Toothbrushes occupy a pivotal position in the maintenance of the health of oral cavity and are most widely employed as the primary means of mechanical plaque control. However, it is noteworthy that inadequate storage practices subsequent to the daily usage of tooth brush, can potentially lead to the colonization and persistence of microorganisms on toothbrushes.

Aim: The current review of literature aims at exploring different ways in which toothbrush storage can be done and find the best methods to adhere.

Methods: A systematic search of the literature was conducted, focused to the storage of tooth brush based on predefined key terms relevant to the title. Four different databases, namely Google scholar, Scopus, PubMed/NCBI and J-Gate, were searched using specific keywords. Both experimental and non-experimental studies, published in “English” were included. The data found so collected was synthesized and analyzed.

Results: After a thorough search of the databases, 34 studies satisfied all the inclusion criteria and were included in this review. The study findings suggested the usage of physical and chemical methods for the storage of used tooth brush to keep it clean and uncontaminated. Further, it was found that 0.2% Chlorhexidine Gluconate and 38% White Vinegar were reported as most efficient for maintaining the cleanliness of the tooth brush.

Conclusion: 0.2% Chlorhexidine Gluconate was the most widely used choice for toothbrush decontamination. The broad spectrum antimicrobial action of the drug, its easy accessibility, economical feasibility and ease of usage may be considered as the possible reasons for the same.

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Introduction:

Oral health is an extremely significant aspect as it has a profound impact on the overall well-being and health of an individual. The oral cavity serves as a direct gateway to the external environment, making it a prime habitat for millions of germs and microorganisms. Among the various microorganisms residing in the oral cavity, some notable ones include *Streptococcus mutans* (responsible for dental caries), β -hemolytic streptococcus (causing sore

throat), *Candida albicans* (leading to oral thrush), *E. coli*, and *Citrobacter* species. Ordinarily, these microorganisms coexist harmlessly within the mouth, seldom causing any diseases or complications. However, certain conditions, e.g., when the host's immune system is compromised i.e. systemic diseases viz AIDS, cancer, or organ transplantations, or when infecting microorganisms are highly virulent or proliferate beyond a certain threshold (compromised oral hygiene in immunocompetent individuals), results in

oral diseases (Periodontal disease and dental caries). Therefore, maintaining proper oral hygiene is crucial in preventing such diseases. The primary method of upholding long term optimal oral hygiene is through the process of tooth brushing. It is estimated that approximately 4 billion people worldwide use toothbrushes, daily for maintaining oral hygiene. This extensive usage of tooth brushes is attributed to their easy availability, simplicity of use, and affordability compared to other means of plaque control e.g. use of chemical antiplaque mouth rinses. While brushing, toothbrushes effectively remove plaque and other soft debris from the surfaces of the tooth. However, during this process, the toothbrush itself becomes contaminated with microorganisms, bodily fluids such as saliva and blood, oral debris, and toothpaste residues etc. Interestingly, if toothbrushes are stored in the same room as a toilet (frequent scenario in developing countries and rural areas), the chances of contamination increase significantly. This is due to the fact that when a toilet is flushed, water sprays upwards, releasing fecal aerosols into the surrounding environment. These aerosols can come into contact with the surface of the toothbrush, posing a potential risk of contamination of the brush leading to transmission of oral diseases. Therefore, it is crucial to store toothbrushes properly to minimize the risk of contamination. Regardless of how thoroughly or frequently one brushes, toothbrushes can act as reservoirs for reintroducing potential pathogens into the oral cavity, if not stored appropriately. Published data states that even after visibly rinsing toothbrushes clean, they may still remain contaminated with potentially pathogenic organisms.^{8,10,15,23,35} Despite the importance of toothbrush storage in maintaining oral health, it is an aspect that is seldom discussed. Only a handful of articles and studies have focused on the various techniques of toothbrush disinfection and storage, aiming to minimize the risk of contamination as much as possible.^{3,6,8,25-26,28,30,34} Thus, the purpose of this systematic review is to explore and examine the different methods of toothbrush storage, providing valuable insights into this often overlooked aspect of oral hygiene.

Methods:

A systematic review of the scientific literature pertaining to this topic was conducted. The review focused on evaluating toothbrush contamination in both healthy individuals and those with oral diseases, guidelines

pertaining to toothbrush, oral care for healthy individuals, and precautionary measures to mitigate toothbrush contamination. To ensure a comprehensive analysis, multiple databases were systematically searched, including PubMed/NCBI, Scopus, Google Scholar, and J-Gate. The review encompassed a diverse range of study designs, including experimental and non-experimental methodologies. Ethical approval and patient consent was not required.

Two independent reviewers conducted a thorough screening process, initially evaluating the abstracts and titles of the identified studies. Records were categorized as 'exclude,' 'include,' or 'uncertain' based on the availability of sufficient information in the abstracts and titles. Exclusion criteria included studies in languages other than English, insufficient information in the abstracts, and unavailability of full texts, unrelated topics/sites, and reviews focused on different subjects. Following this screening process, the full texts of relevant papers were obtained for further examination. The standard guidelines of PRISMA were followed for the screening of literature.

Data extraction was then done from all studies that met the eligibility criteria. Data synthesis and analysis was carried out to draw conclusions.

Results:

Out of the initial pool of 748 studies, a rigorous selection process led to the inclusion of 34 studies in this review. The selection criteria were applied to exclude studies that did not meet the specified inclusion criteria.

The initial search yielded a total of 748 studies. Among these, 299 relevant articles were found on PubMed/NCBI, followed by 193 articles on J-Gate and 56 articles on Scopus. Google Scholar also produced a substantial number of search results, with 3260 records identified. From these, the first 200 relevant articles were selected for further screening. In the end, a total of 34 studies were deemed suitable for inclusion in this systematic search. (Fig.1) These studies provided valuable insights into toothbrush contamination, oral care guidelines, and strategies to minimize the risk of contamination, facilitating a comprehensive analysis of the research topic at hand.

A descriptive summary of the included literature has been presented in table 1. Included studies highlighted numerous approaches for toothbrush decontamination. Among these methods, Chlorhexidine emerged as the most prominent method for toothbrush sterilization, being

mentioned in 12 studies.^{3,4,9,12,14-15,17,21,26,29,31,34} Additionally, 1% sodium hypochlorite was a preferred option,^{4,9,12,17,20} mentioned in 5 studies. 38% White vinegar and Listerine were the next preferred choices,^{9,11,13-14,18,20-21,23} each mentioned in 4 studies. 3% neem juice and Triclosan were mentioned in 2 studies.^{4,8,16,28} Physical methods of decontamination, such as UV sanitization and microwave irradiation,^{6,11,19,26-27,31} were discussed in 5 and 2 studies respectively. There were isolated studies which mentioned the use of 7.5% povidone iodine,²⁶ 3.5% sodium chloride,²³ toothbrush spray,²² 4% disodium EDTA,²⁸ 10% sodium perborate,²⁷ 2% glutaraldehyde,¹ charcoal,³⁰ and ozone also

for the purpose of maintaining a clean tooth brush.⁵ Interestingly, a few natural methods were also explored for the purpose of toothbrush decontamination, although there was only one study each for these agents such as garlic,²⁷ green tea,²⁷ and guava leaf extract.³⁴ These substances were investigated for their potential antimicrobial properties and their ability to effectively decontaminate toothbrushes. While further research is needed to validate their efficacy and safety, these natural alternatives show promise as potential options for toothbrush sterilization.

Identification of studies via databases and registers

Figure 1 - Prisma Flowchart

Table-1- showing the descriptive summary of the eligible studies

S. No.	Study	Purpose	Type of Study	Samples	Results
1.	Dayoub et al. (1977)	To determine the degree of bacterial contamination of toothbrushes after contamination and storage in vented containers or in air.	Experimental	N=103 tooth brushes	Toothbrushes that are left exposed in the open air after use tend to experience a faster reduction in the number of bacteria compared to brushes stored in closed containers.
2.	Glass & Jensen (1994)	To evaluate toothbrush design and UV sanitation on microbial growth	Experimental study	N=72 tooth brushes	Exposing toothbrushes to UV sanitizing effectively eliminates bacteria, while viruses have the ability to survive on toothbrushes for up to 24 hours. The design, color, opacity, and arrangement of bristles on a tooth brush play a significant role in harboring and retaining microorganisms.
3.	Nelson et al. (2000)	To determine the level of contamination of toothbrushes by Streptococci mutans using microbiological identification, to access the bacterial contamination using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and to evaluate the efficacy of two toothbrush disinfectants	Randomized control trial	N=19 tooth brushes	Group I (0.12% chlorhexidine gluconate) & Group II (1% sodium hypochlorite) demonstrated no bacterial growth, indicating that immersion in these solutions is an effective method for disinfecting toothbrushes. In contrast, Group III (sterile tap water) showed bacterial growth, highlighting the limited effectiveness of using sterile tap water for toothbrush disinfection.
4.	Warren DP et al (2001)	To evaluate the effect of a Triclosan-containing toothpaste on the residual anaerobic microbial contamination of toothbrushes.	Experimental	N=20 patients	The application of toothpaste resulted in a decrease in residual microbial contamination for two out of the three organisms tested. However, the observed reduction in isolation frequencies was not statistically significant. Therefore, further research is recommended to explore this area in more detail and obtain more conclusive results.
5.	Nelson –Filho P. et al(2004)	To evaluate by culture and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) the contamination of toothbrushes of 30 children (5-7 yrs. old) by <i>Mutans streptococci</i> (MS) when dentifrices with or without Triclosan are used	Clinical trial	N=30 patients	After a single use, the bristles of the toothbrushes were found to be contaminated with Mutans streptococci. However, the presence of Triclosan in the dentifrice significantly decreased the bacterial contamination on these toothbrushes.
6.	Sato S et al (2004)	To evaluate bacterial survival rate on toothbrushes after brushing and the efficacy of their decontamination by spraying antimicrobial solutions.	Experimental	N=30 patients	Toothbrushes, even after brushing, were found to harbor both obligate anaerobic and aerobic bacteria. However, the use of sprays containing cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) and the basic formulation showed promising results in reducing toothbrush contamination. These approaches proved to be effective and beneficial in minimizing the presence of microorganisms on toothbrushes.
7.	Mehta et al. 2007)	To determine the extent of bacterial contamination of toothbrushes after use, efficacy of chlorhexidine and Listerine in decontamination, and effectiveness of covering the tooth brush head with a cap.	Experimental	N=10 patients	During use, toothbrushes can get contaminated and the presence of moisture and organic matter can promote bacterial growth. This contamination can lead to colonization and potential infection. Using caps on toothbrushes can actually increase bacterial growth. In terms of effectiveness, chlorhexidine was found to be more effective than Listerine in reducing bacterial contamination.
8.	M. Efstratiou et al (2007)	To examine the contamination and the survival rate of periodontopathic and cariogenic species on new tooth brushes with antibacterial properties (coated bristles with Triclosan), after a single use in periodontitis patients. The decontamination effects of tooth paste were also evaluated.	Experimental	N=10 patients	The toothbrush with Triclosan coated tufts did not effectively prevent bacterial contamination. However, the use of toothpaste significantly reduced the level of bacterial contamination on the toothbrushes.

9.	Ayşegül O et al (2007)	To determine the level of contamination by mutans streptococci on the toothbrushes of children using microbial identification and evaluate the efficacy of 0.12% chlorhexidine spray vs chlorhexidine mouthwash as toothbrush disinfectants	Experimental	N=71 patients	Toothbrushes soaked in sterile saline solution exhibited high levels of mutans streptococci counts and biofilm formation. There was no significant difference observed between the groups using chlorhexidine mouthwash and chlorhexidine spray. Both methods demonstrated the ability to effectively disinfect the toothbrushes when maintained for a duration of 2 hours.
10.	Bezirtzoglou E et al (2008)	To study the ozone experimental effect upon toothbrushes microflora was estimated microbiologically before and after saturation with ozone gas	In-vitro experimental study	N=50 tooth brushes	The application of ozone was discovered to effectively eliminate the microbiota on toothbrush bristles after regular brushing. The greatest effectiveness in decontamination was observed when toothbrushes were exposed to ozone for a duration of 30 minutes. However, shorter exposure times were found to be ineffective in achieving significant decontamination.
11.	LA Turner et al (2009)	To determine the effectiveness of chlorhexidine- coated toothbrush filaments in reducing quantities of bacteria.	Randomized control trial	N=64 patients	The findings of the study showed that there was no significant difference in the amount of bacteria remaining on the toothbrush bristles between the control group and the experimental groups. This was observed across both selective and non-selective media after a period of 30 days.
12.	Balappanavar AY et al (2009)	To test the efficacy of 3% neem, 2% Triclosan, 0.25 chlorhexidine gluconate and 1% sodium hypochlorite as toothbrush disinfectants against Streptococcus mutans	Double-blind, linear crossover, within-group comparative experimental trial	N= 40 patients	All of the solutions tested in the study were found to be effective in decontaminating toothbrushes. However, it was observed that the solution containing 3% neem had a higher efficacy compared to the other solutions.
13.	Komiyama EY et al (2010)	To evaluate alternative methods for the disinfection of toothbrushes considering that most of the previously proposed methods are expensive and cannot be easily implemented.	Experimental	N=200 tooth brushes	The Triclosan-containing dentifrice solutions tested in the study showed promising results as effective and safe alternatives for toothbrush disinfection. They were found to be cost-effective and easy to use. Additionally, the vinegar solution tested also demonstrated a reduction in the presence of S. aureus, S. mutans, and S. pyogenes on the tooth brushes.
14.	Konidala U et al (2011)	To evaluate the effectiveness of different disinfectant agents in decontaminating the toothbrushes, and to evaluate the children, parents and the community on the decontamination of toothbrushes	Experimental	N=50 patients	Hexidine, 3% hydrogen peroxide, and Listerine were found to be highly effective in completely eliminating microorganisms on the toothbrushes. Among these options, 3% hydrogen peroxide stood out as the most cost-effective choice.
15.	DMP Spolidorio et al (2011)	To investigate the effectiveness of two alternatives methods for the disinfection of oral cleaning devices	Experimental	N=16 tooth brushes	Microwave irradiation was found to be a successful and efficient method for disinfecting tongue cleaners and toothbrushes. In just 1 minute of microwave exposure, all the contaminating microorganisms were inactivated. Alternatively, immersion in a 3.78% sodium perborate solution required 2-3 hours to achieve the same level of disinfection for C. albicans and S. mutans/S. aureus.
16.	Gujjari SK et al (2011)	To evaluate the sanitization of tooth brushes previously contaminated by various oral microorganisms using a domestic microwave oven and commercial ultraviolet (UV) light toothbrush sanitizer	Randomized control trial	N=30 patients	This study provides evidence supporting the effectiveness of microwave irradiation as a disinfectant for bacteria and fungi on toothbrushes.

17.	Sheikh N.S et al (2014)	To evaluate the bacterial survival rate on toothbrushes and efficacy of their decontamination by 4% EDTA, 10% sodium perborate and 3% neem juice.	Randomized Control Trial	N=40 subjects	4% disodium EDTA and 3% neem juice were 100% effective in decontaminating toothbrushes, while 10% sodium perborate had 40% effectiveness. Distilled water showed the least effectiveness. Neem juice is a preferred option due to its non-toxicity, cost-effectiveness, and practicality.
18.	Peker I. et al (2014)	To evaluate the effectiveness of alternative methods for toothbrush disinfection	In- vivo laboratory study	N=280 tooth brushes	100% white vinegar and 1% NaOCl were found effective for toothbrush disinfection.
19.	Tomar P et al (2014)	To evaluate the efficacy of 0.2% chlorhexidine (CHX) gluconate solution and ultra violet(UV) tooth brush sanitizer for toothbrush disinfection	Experimental	N=15 tooth brushes	UV rays, CHX, and normal saline all demonstrated effectiveness in reducing bacterial counts on tooth brushes. Among these methods, UV ray treatment was found to be more effective than CHX and normal saline.
20.	Do Nascimento C et al (2014)	To evaluate the efficacy of three antimicrobial solutions on the disinfection of toothbrushes after storage in closed containers	Randomized control trial	N=16 patients	The culture and DNA checkerboard methods confirmed the presence of bacterial contamination on the toothbrushes. Mouth rinses containing 0.12% chlorhexidine gluconate demonstrated higher effectiveness in reducing bacterial colonization on the toothbrushes.
21.	P J Swathy Anand et al (2016)	To compare efficacy of 3% neem, garlic of concentration 4.15 mg/ml and green tea of concentration 40mg/ml with 0.2% chlorhexidine mouth wash as toothbrush disinfectants	In-vitro comparative experimental trial	N=75 patients	Neem, garlic, and green tea were found to be equally effective as chlorhexidine in disinfecting toothbrushes. These herbal products can serve as potent alternatives to chlorhexidine for maintaining toothbrush hygiene.
22.	Basman A, Peker I et al (2016)	To compare the efficacy of using a dishwasher or different chemical agents, including 0.12% chlorhexidine gluconate, 2% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl), a mouth rinse containing essential oils & alcohol, and 50% white vinegar for tooth brush disinfection.	Experimental	N=60 patients	Among the tested methods, 50% white vinegar proved to be the most effective in eliminating all tested bacterial species. It was followed by 2% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl), a mouth rinse containing essential oils and alcohol, 0.12% chlorhexidine gluconate, dishwasher use, and tap water (control). Notably, white vinegar offers not only high efficacy but also cost-effectiveness, easy accessibility, and suitability for various household tasks.
23.	R.vignesh et al (2017)	To assess the antimicrobial potency of aqueous extract of <i>Psidium guajava</i> leaves in two different concentrations as a toothbrush disinfectant against three oral bacterial species.	Experimental	N=100 tooth brushes	Guava leaf extracts have demonstrated comparable efficacy to 0.2% chlorhexidine as a natural disinfectant for contaminated toothbrushes. This simple and easily prepared solution offers an organic alternative for toothbrush disinfection in household settings.
24.	Mavani et al (2018)	To evaluate if vinegar & vinegar with 3.5% sodium chloride could be used as an alternative to chlorhexidine gluconate for disinfection of toothbrushes	Randomized Control Trial	N= 24 patients	The most effective solution was proven to be a combination of 38% white vinegar and 3.5% sodium chloride.
25.	Daeng et al (2018)	To know the effectiveness of uses of UV sanitation equipment on the reduction of bacterial colony on toothbrush	Experimental	N= 11 patients	The microbial species identified on the toothbrushes included <i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> , <i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> , <i>Proteus mirabilis</i> , <i>Alkaligenes faecalis</i> , <i>Enterobacter hafniae</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , and <i>Citrobacter freundii</i> . UV sanitation for 7 minutes resulted in a reduction of microorganisms, but longer exposure times were found to be more effective in completely deactivating the microorganisms. Therefore, it is recommended to use the UV sanitation tool for a longer duration to ensure thorough deactivation of microorganisms.

26.	Ah-Reum Shin and Seoul-Hee Nam (2018)	To investigate the antimicrobial effect of the UV toothbrush sterilizer and various disinfectants on the toothbrush.	Experimental	N=20 patients	Continuous toothbrush disinfection is crucial for preventing cross-infection and should be performed at a cost-effective rate. The findings of this study suggest that utilizing disinfectants such as 0.2% chlorhexidine (CHX) and 7.5% povidone-iodine (PVI) are highly recommended methods for effective tooth brush disinfection. By employing these disinfection approaches, the risk of transmitting harmful micro-organisms can be significantly reduced, promoting better oral hygiene and overall health.
27.	Thamke MV et al (2018)	To evaluate the bacterial contamination and antimicrobial efficacy of charcoal bristles compared to no charcoal bristles in used tooth brushes	Experimental	N=50 patients	The study revealed a notable and statistically significant distinction in bacterial counts between different types of toothbrush bristles. After one week of use, the charcoal bristles exhibited lower colony-forming units (CFUs) compared to the non-charcoal bristles. Additionally, the presence of a zone of inhibition surrounding the charcoal toothbrush bristles provided evidence of their antimicrobial properties. These findings highlight the potential benefits of using charcoal toothbrushes in reducing bacterial growth and promoting oral hygiene.
28.	Nissar I. et al (2019)	To compare the efficacy of three different chemical agents as tooth brush disinfectant	Randomized control trial	N=40 patients	All methods tested effectively reduced bacterial counts, with NaOCl (2%) being the most effective, followed by Listerine, chlorhexidine, and water. NaOCl demonstrated high efficiency as a disinfectant, while Listerine and chlorhexidine also showed significant efficacy in reducing bacterial counts
29.	Sabarish R. et al (2019)	To assess the influence of a decontaminating agent (sterile water-control/ chlorhexidine mouthwash, herbal mouthwash) on the properties of tooth brush bristles following storage for 24hrs by means of scanning electron microscopy(SEM) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR).	Experimental	N=24 tooth brushes	Regular toothbrush decontamination is recommended, although it may lead to increased wear of the bristles and potential damage to the teeth. Among the different methods of toothbrush decontamination, the use of herbal mouthwash had the least impact on the properties of the toothbrush bristles.
30.	Ralephenya T.R et al (2020)	To evaluate microbial contamination of toothbrushes and the efficacy of different oral disinfectant agents in their decontamination	Experimental	N=98 tooth brushes	Toothbrushes were primarily contaminated with Coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS). Brushtox, a toothbrush spray, proved to be the most effective method, reducing the number of contaminated tooth brushes by 90%. Oral health practitioners should educate patients about the importance of disinfecting toothbrushes.
31.	Manohar R. et al (2022)	To assess the microbial contamination of toothbrush with and without a protective cap and to find the significance of the same against microbial contamination.	Ex-vivo observational study	N=40 tooth brushes	Toothbrushes without protective caps had significantly higher microbial contamination, while toothbrushes with protective caps showed no growth. Using a tooth brush with a protective cap is recommended for maintaining oral hygiene and overall well-being.
32.	Assari A S, Mohammed Mahrous M, Ahmad Y A et al (2022)	To identify the most rapid, effective and affordable method for toothbrush decontamination.	Experimental	N=55 patients	All sterilization methods effectively reduced bacterial counts on toothbrushes. Sterilization with 2% glutaraldehyde and 3% hydrogen peroxide solutions resulted in the most significant reduction in bacterial counts. The toothbrushes were colonized by various bacterial species, with <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> , <i>Sacrina</i> , and <i>Streptococcus pneumonia</i> being the most prevalent.

33.	Pradeep S, Nandini G, Hiranmavi S et al (2022)	To assess the microbial contamination of toothbrushes and methods of their contamination.	Experimental	N= 160 patients	Dettol was the most effective disinfectant for tooth brushes, followed by Listerine and 0.2% chlorhexidine gluconate. Tap water was ineffective for toothbrush decontamination. Daily disinfection and storing tooth brushes in a dry place are recommended for optimal oral hygiene and overall health.
34.	Alvarez G et al (2023)	To determine the antiseptic efficacy of 0.05% chlorhexidine + 0.05% vccetylpyridinium chloride mouth wash on toothbrushes.	Experimental	N=12 tooth brushes	The 0.05% CHX + 0.05% CPC mouthwash effectively reduces live bacteria on toothbrushes, as demonstrated by both culture and culture-independent methods. However, the culture method showed a 10-fold higher difference in live cell count between the control and treatment groups compared to the vPCR method. Further research is needed to investigate this disparity.

Discussion:

The hygiene of the main portal of maintenance of oral hygiene i.e., the tooth brush has been often overlooked and is much understudied. Toothbrushes have been identified as potential reservoirs for bacteria, including fecal-like coliform bacteria, which can be transferred to the toothbrush surface through contact with contaminated surfaces or airborne particles released during toilet flushing. Achieving optimal oral health goes beyond regular brushing practices and extends to ensuring that the toothbrush itself remains free from microbial contamination. There is an urgent need to educate individuals about proper toothbrush storage techniques. By doing so, we can ensure that the oral cavity remains truly healthy and free from the potential threats posed by contaminated toothbrushes. This review of literature has been conducted to showcase the existing methods of tooth brush storage and update the readers regarding the best methods as evident on the basis of contemporary published literature available.

Although literature on toothbrush sanitization is limited, the findings suggested that various methods are available for toothbrush sanitization, can be classified as chemical or natural means. Among the chemical methods, 0.2% Chlorhexidine Gluconate was found to be the most preferred choice due to its cost-effectiveness and availability, followed by Listerine and 1% Sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl). Natural methods for toothbrush decontamination were less common but equally effective. For instance, 38% White Vinegar and 3% Neem Juice were identified as suitable options due to their antibacterial

properties, which are commonly found in household. UV sanitization was also investigated as a means of toothbrush decontamination. Research by Glass and Jensen¹¹ indicated that UV exposure for at least 7 minutes can effectively kill bacteria, but viruses may survive on toothbrush surfaces for up to 24 hours. This highlights the importance of proper sanitization methods to prevent the transmission of pathogens. Research conducted by Dayoub et al.⁷ demonstrated that toothbrushes stored in closed containers or exposed to infected surfaces exhibited greater bacterial quantities compared to those left uncovered to the air. These findings were supported by a study conducted by Mehta et al.¹⁴, which indicated that the use of a protective element like cap for toothbrush storage exhibited an upsurge in the rate of bacterial survival. On the other hand,

Glass¹¹ observed that increased humidity in the environment enhanced the survival of bacteria on toothbrushes, suggesting that environmental factors may influence bacterial colonization. Contradicting these findings, a study by Ganesh A et al. reported that toothbrushes stored without protective caps had higher microbial loads,¹⁰ indicating that the usage of protective caps may be recommended for maintaining good oral hygiene.

Several studies have identified various bacterial species contaminating toothbrush bristles. The most dominant species include *S. mutans*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. Other less prevalent bacterial species found include *Enterobacter cloacal*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and *Alkaligenes faecalis*. These findings underscore the

need for effective toothbrush hygiene practices to minimize bacterial colonization and potential oral health risks. The CDC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention)³⁶ provides several recommendations for the storage of toothbrushes to maintain oral hygiene and minimize the risk of infection. Firstly, it is important to avoid sharing toothbrushes as they can harbor germs even after rinsing, which can be particularly problematic for individuals with weakened immune systems. After brushing, it is advised to thoroughly rinse the toothbrush with tap water until it is completely clean and then allow it to air-dry in an upright position. It is also recommended to store individual toothbrushes separately, ensuring they do not come into contact with each other within the same holder. The CDC³⁶ advises against soaking toothbrushes in disinfecting solutions or mouthwash, as these may actually facilitate the spread of germs in certain conditions. Additionally, there is no need to use dishwashers, microwaves, or ultraviolet devices to disinfect toothbrushes, as these methods can potentially damage the toothbrush itself. Furthermore, covering toothbrushes or storing them in closed containers should be avoided, as this can create a favorable environment for bacterial growth. Finally, the CDC³⁶ suggests replacing toothbrushes every 3-4 months, or sooner if the bristles appear worn out. The primary reason for replacement is to ensure effective tooth brushing rather than concerns about increased germ accumulation. By following these recommendations, individuals can maintain a clean and hygienic toothbrush, promoting good oral health practices.

In addition to proper toothbrush storage, it is important to emphasize the significance of regular toothbrush replacement. Over time, the bristles of a toothbrush wear out and become less effective in removing plaque and debris from the teeth. The American Dental Association (ADA)³² also recommends replacing the toothbrush every three to four months, or sooner if the bristles become frayed. This ensures that toothbrush remains effective in maintaining proper oral hygiene. Additionally, it is advisable to replace the toothbrush after recovering from an illness, as it may harbor bacteria or viruses that can potentially re-infect. By adhering to these recommendations and incorporating regular toothbrush replacement into oral care routine, we can maximize the benefits of brushing and contribute to long-term oral health.

Conclusion:

Based on this comprehensive review of the existing literature, it can be concluded that the field of toothbrush decontamination is relatively under-researched. Within the limitations, the findings suggest that the use of Chlorhexidine gluconate is the most widely employed and efficient method to reduce bacterial load, thus can be considered as the best practice for maintaining a clean tooth brush. In addition to chemical substances, there is a growing interest in exploring the potential of natural antibacterial agents such as neem juice and garlic as adjuncts in toothbrush decontamination. Incorporating these natural substances into oral hygiene practices may provide additional benefits in maintaining a healthy oral environment. However, further research is needed to investigate the efficacy and safety of these natural adjuncts in toothbrush decontamination to support their practical application.

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